

Transitions to University: Insights on FET Learners' Pathways to Higher Education in Ireland – Lessons for Policy and Practice

FETRC (Further Education & Training Research Centre)

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

AONTAS	The National Irish Adult Learning Organisation
APM	Average Precision Mark
CAO	Central Applications Office
DARE	Disability Access Route to Education
DCU	Dublin City University
DES	Department of Education and Skills
DFHERIS	Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science
EFQ	European Framework of Qualifications
ETB	Education and Training Board
FET	Further Education and Training
HE	Higher Education
HEA	Higher Education Authority
HEAR	Higher Education Access Route
HEI	Higher Education Institution
HELS	Higher Education Links Scheme
ICT	Information, Communications and Technology
INDECON	Independent Economic Research and Consultancy Organisation
NFQ	National Framework of Qualifications
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PLC	Post-Leaving Certificate Course
QIIO	Quality and Institutional Insight Office, DCU

QQI	Quality and Qualifications Ireland
RIA	Royal Irish Academy
SEC	State Examinations Commission
SOLAS	An tSeirbhís Oideachais Leanúnaigh agus Scileanna
STEM	Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics
VEC	Vocational Education Committee
VET	Vocational Education and Training

Executive Summary

This report set out to explore the student experiences of first year Dublin City University (DCU) undergraduate students who qualified for entry onto two undergraduate programmes, DC115 Accounting and Finance and DC121 Computer Science via the Quality and Qualifications Ireland (QQI) Further Education and Training (FET) entry route. The research highlights the challenges and successes of first year DC115 and DC121 students who previously studied at a FET College prior to entering DCU. Due to challenges in qualitative data collection which resulted in only one student interview taking place, the challenges and successes outlined in this report rely heavily upon available quantitative data and literature. Despite the high acceptance rates and high progression to second semester of year one, particularly in Computer Science, FET entrants on these programmes exhibit lower pass rates in mathematics and practical or laboratory-based modules in comparison to Leaving Certificate entrants and students entering through other cohorts such as HEAR, DARE and Sports Scholarship pathways. The difference in academic outcomes between FET cohorts and other students may be attributed to FET students' external commitments and the inherent difficulties of these subjects in higher education. It is worth noting that academic outcomes appear to be more challenging for DCU students who entered through the QQI route and are also within the age band to be considered for mature student entry criteria. The literature highlighted within the study also identifies potential gaps in professional guidance within FET colleges and schools, which may impede the smooth progression of students to higher education.

Limitations in data collection and access to the potential student sample cohort posed challenges, but the findings underscore the need for enhanced academic support, improved data tracking, and stronger partnerships between FET institutions and DCU to better prepare QQI-FET entrants for academic success.

The report concludes with recommendations aimed at improving the support structures and pathways for QQI-FET students, ensuring they are equipped to meet the demands of higher education and achieve their full potential.

1 Introduction

This report attempts to capture the student experience of transitioning from FET to DCU in two specific undergraduate degree programmes. It focuses on the transition from a QQI level 5 or 6 accredited Post-Leaving Certificate (PLC) programme to a QQI level 8 undergraduate programme within the School of Computing and Engineering and the Business School at DCU. As highlighted in DCU's Stronger Connections Roundtable Report (2021), the research signifies DCU's commitment to supporting the development of a more coherent tertiary sector by aiming to capture the FET to DCU student experience. Findings from the Roundtable consultation with key stakeholders in the FET sector provide a basis for the FET to DCU project aims. In addition to developing research as an active response to stakeholder engagement, placing the student voice at the centre of this project reflects DCU's overall vision which aims to 'transform lives and societies through listening, linking and leading for a better future' (DCU, 2023).

The development of FET to HE pathways has been driven by European and National policy developments, legislation and governance changes in the Irish Education system (O'Sullivan, 2021). While progress in establishing pathways from FET to HE can be traced back to the 1990s, advancements in policy and legislation in the past two decades have escalated the development process. The establishment of a ten-level Irish National Framework of Qualifications in 2003 provided a common language for education and training qualifications to be compared and understood across different sectors and levels of the Irish education system (QQI, 2020). Furthermore, the Qualifications and Quality Assurance (Education and Training) Act 2012 implemented governance changes in the overall FET sector resulting in a more streamlined, coherent structure for the sector. The first Further Education and Training strategy 2014-2019 recognised the importance of developing FET to HE transition for societal and individual economic and holistic benefits (SOLAS, 2014). Within the higher education sector, the National Access Plan 2015-2019 saw FET learners included in the widening participation target cohort groups (HEA, 2015). In recent developments, governance of FET and HE sectors came under the same, new, government department, the Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science (DFHERIS) in 2020.

As outlined in the vision for a unified tertiary education system, the newly formed department recognises the significance of developing FET to HE pathways to support the development of a more equitable and diverse tertiary education cohort (DFHERIS, 2022).

While there has been much advancement in the development of FET to HE transitions, systemic and administrative barriers continue to exist for students applying to HE via a QQI-FET qualification. These barriers are most apparent when comparing progression opportunities for students applying to HE with different education qualifications. Students who apply to HE on the basis of State Examination Committee (SEC) Leaving Certificate Examination results have a wider range of progression options and access to national equity access initiatives such as HEAR (Higher Education Access Route) and DARE (Disability Access Route to Education) schemes which aim to increase participation of underrepresented cohorts in higher education (O’Sullivan, 2021).

1.1 Aims and Objectives of the Research

Set within the developing landscape of the Irish Tertiary Education system, this study aimed to investigate how students on two specific undergraduate programmes, DC115 Accounting and Finance and DC121 Computer Science who joined DCU via the QQI Further Education and Training (FET) route, were experiencing their programmes and progressing in their studies. To capture the student journey from FET to DCU the study set out to investigate the following four areas of interest. However, due to limited qualitative data collection, objectives one and two were not achieved. The report relies upon available quantitative data and literature to inform objectives three and four.

1. Student experiences and understandings of the application and CAO process including guidance and information sources.
2. The admission process into DCU including online registration and engagement with registration.
3. Academic student experience and assessment performance outcomes of first year undergraduate students.
4. Non-academic student experience and engagement with DCU student support.

2 Literature Review

The literature review draws upon available data of FET provision and students' experiences of transitions from FET to higher education (HE) in the Irish, European and Wider Global contexts. The first section of the literature provides an overview of Post-Leaving Certificate (PLC) provision in the Irish landscape. The current systemic challenges of FET to HE transitions as well as benefits of increasing pathways are also discussed. The second section explores FET to HE transitions from the student perspective, specifically, the reasons why students transition, barriers to HE engagement and benefits of achieving a HE qualification.

2.1 The FET Sector- Context, Developments and Societal Perceptions

The following section provides an overview of PLC provision within the FET landscape. In addition, the literature includes policy and governance changes which have supported the development of FET to HE pathways in the Irish context. The benefits of increasing pathways between different levels of education and training systems are discussed. This section also highlights current systemic and administrative barriers which inhibit further development of pathways. Finally, the literature focuses on societal perceptions of the FET sector at both National and European level.

2.1.1 PLC provision in the Irish FET Landscape

The FET sector offers a wide range of learning opportunities across a range of programmes and settings for people over the age of sixteen. From a European perspective, the Vocational Education and Training Sector (VET) is largely aimed at providing vocational and occupation specific programmes to meet skill demands in specific sectors. In comparison, Ireland's FET sector aims to provide a broader range of education and training outcome options which include vocational, non-occupation and occupation-specific qualifications (Cedefop, 2017). Unlike many EU countries, Ireland has no upper secondary school VET. The Post-Leaving Certificate (PLC) programme accounts for the largest proportion of learning engagement across the FET sector. PLC courses provide learners with the opportunity to achieve a QQI major award at National Framework of Qualifications (NFQ) levels 5 and 6 across a range of disciplines (SOLAS, 2020, McGuinness et al., 2018). Post-Leaving Certificate programme accreditation at QQI level 5 is equivalent to the SEC Leaving Certificate Ordinary programme on the National Framework of Qualifications which takes place during the last two years of post-primary school provision. The

Leaving Certificate programme provides students with the opportunity to obtain a SEC Leaving Certificate Qualification at QQI level 5 on the NFQ. While both PLC and SEC academic outcomes are equivalent on the NFQ, maximum points outcomes applied to each qualification for the purpose of higher education entry vary significantly. The maximum points allocation for SEC candidates to HE is 625 points. In comparison, the maximum points allocation for QQI candidates is 390 points. The difference in maximum points attainment for QQI and SEC entrants could further add to negative societal perceptions of the overall PLC qualification. While the Leaving Certificate Course is targeted at full-time students in post-primary school settings, PLC courses are open to young people and adults returning to Education and Training (SOLAS, 2020). The two core outcomes of PLC courses are progression to employment and higher education (SOLAS, 2020a). Research shows the majority of PLC to HE transitions take place across the same area of study with a large number of these transitions taking place within the same academic year (Ibid.).

PLC students are a diverse cohort of learners who have different personal, academic and socio-economic backgrounds (College Connect, 2023; McGuinness et al., 2018). Recent research found that 62% of PLC learners are within the 200-400 point Leaving Certificate points achievement band (McGuinness et al., 2018). While historically, PLC provision was a female dominated sector, recent data shows a change in gender participation with a 50% split in male and female cohorts receiving a QQI level 5 and 6 award (QQI, 2024). While it appears the overall QQI award outcomes have achieved gender balance, specific analysis of students receiving ICT QQI major awards at levels 5 and 6 suggests that they are predominantly male (Ibid.).

2.1.2 The development of FET to HE Pathways

Within the context of the Irish tertiary education system a large proportion of HE programmes offer entry routes for learners applying with a PLC qualification (O’Sullivan, 2021). Historically, pathways between FET and HE providers were established through local institutional agreements (Rami et al, 2016). While the existence of institutional relationships is important for QQI-FET to HE transitions, recent developments within the HE sector have seen higher education institutions such as DCU move towards accepting generic PLC qualifications at NFQ levels 5 and 6 as entry to undergraduate degree programmes. Currently, DCU facilitates QQI-FET entrants on 61 of their 70 undergraduate level 8 degree programmes.

FET to HE pathways are facilitated through the Higher Education Links Scheme (HELs). First established in the 1990s, the HELs scheme initially facilitated transitions between Vocational Education Committees (VEC) which were statutory local education and training bodies responsible for the delivery of adult education and some secondary school programmes up until 2013 to Institutes of Technology. The scheme currently facilitates QQI level 5 and 6 applications to higher education institutions. In addition to the establishment of the HELs scheme, the development of the European and NFQ has provided a structure for qualifications to be compared across the National and European systems (O’Sullivan, 2021; QQI, 2020). The NFQ and EFQ have provided a framework which facilitates common language between education and training providers therefore allowing greater permeability (European Commission, 2018). FET to HE pathways are recognised as a significant indicator of overall sectoral success within both FET and HEI policy. The National Access plan 2015-2019, which aims to support access to higher education for underrepresented groups, recognised the significance of QQI-FET entry routes in supporting target cohorts to access HE. A target of increasing QQI-FET entrants to HE by 10% was established as a Key Performance Indicator in the 2015-2019 policy (HEA, 2015). The QQI-FET entrant route continues to be acknowledged as a valued bridge into higher education in the current National Access Plan, however there is no dedicated progression target outlined (HEA, 2022). Within the FET sector both DCU, National and Regional policy has outlined commitments to increasing QQI-FET to HE pathways by 10% over a set period of time (DCU, 2023a; SOLAS, 2022; SOLAS, 2020). Furthermore, the establishment of the new Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science (DFHERIS) in 2020 set out a vision of a more unified tertiary education system that provides clear and multiple pathways for learners and more balanced resourcing and funding for FET and HE sectors (DFHERIS, 2022).

2.1.3 Current Systemic and Administrative Barriers in the context of QQI-FET to HE transitions

While there has been much progress in the development of QQI-FET to HE pathways at a national level, administrative and systemic barriers continue to exist for QQI-FET entrants. As highlighted by O’Sullivan, regardless of the equal level of NFQ qualifications between QQI level 5 major awards and traditional Leaving Certificate examinations, current processes and initiatives are often more advantageous for State Examinations Committee (SEC) applicants (2021). Currently, national equity access initiatives such as HEAR and DARE are not open to QQI applicants. Given that available

data shows that 59.98% of FET learners engaged in 2019 fell within the marginally 'below average' to 'extremely disadvantaged' deprivation index score, access to the HEAR initiative could be hugely beneficial in supporting those experiencing socio economic disadvantage to progress to higher education (SOLAS, 2019). While the expansion of HEAR and DARE to FET entrants was proposed in the National Access Plan 2015-2019, the implementation of this recommendation has not yet been implemented (HEA, 2015, p.40).

Furthermore, not every undergraduate qualification has a QQI-FET entry route. Programmes that facilitate QQI-FET entry applicants are allocated through two different processes, a quota-based system or a points-based system (O'Sullivan, 2021). Typically, Technological Universities operate a points-based system with the latter Universities using a quota-based allocation model which ring fences a specific number of places on undergraduate programmes for QQI-FET entrants. DCU adopts a quota-based system to allocate QQI-FET entry. The differentiation in allocation approaches between Technological Universities and other HEIs potentially adds further complexity to understanding FET to HE pathways from the student's perspective.

The potential maximum point allocation for HE entry purposes varies significantly between QQI-FET and SEC applicants. It could be argued that differences in recognition between QQI-FET and SEC qualifications are a consequence of the poor societal standing of the FET sector in the Irish context.

2.1.4 Societal perceptions of FET

The FET sector has been referred to as the Cinderella or the poor relation of the Irish Education system (O'Sullivan 2017; McGuinness et al., 2014). A European-wide survey conducted in 2016 indicated 81% of surveyed participants in the Irish context agreed or strongly agreed that general education has a more credible standing than further education and training (Eurostat, 2016). At European level, FET provision is often regarded as an option for students who obtain lower academic grades (Condon, 2018). While FET is a valued sector in certain countries such as Germany, other countries such as Denmark and Sweden are experiencing negative consequences of poor societal perception of the sector (Christensen et al., 2024; Cedefop, 2022).

In addition to views on the overall FET sector, research shows careers linked to training in the sector are also subject to negative stereotypes

(Cedefop et al., 2021). Poor societal standing of careers associated with FET has the potential to result in future skilled worker shortages which are dependent upon FET training to survive. Interestingly, some countries in the European context are increasing permeability to encourage uptake of FET qualifications. For instance, recent legislative changes in Sweden and Germany have both significantly increased vertical permeability between FET and HE, with learners from both countries now able to access higher education with a post-secondary FET qualification (Cedefop, 2022; Aarkrog, 2020; Cedefop, 2017).

2.1.5 Impact of poor societal FET standing- The student perspective

The impact of the poor societal perception of the FET sector has consequences for FET learners. In research conducted with PLC students in the Irish context, poor FET social status in comparison to HE has led to ‘negative internal manifestations and for some a sense of embarrassment for ending up in FE college as opposed to university’ (College Connect, 2023, p.9). In the context of exploring adult learners’ opinions of the FET sector in the Irish societal context, Maloney offered similar findings (2021). Within Maloney’s study, FET adult learners noted a marked societal difference between HE and FET settings stating students engaged in HE education are considered ‘smarter’ than their FET counterparts (Ibid.). Furthermore, the negative perceptions of the FET sector were noted in the context of the UK where traditionally the Further Education (FE) route is associated with non-academic pathways and is of less value in comparison to higher education (Fuller et al., 2012). Similar to findings in the Irish context, this research identifies schools as an area in which the misconception of FE manifests (Ibid.). This phenomenon has also been recorded in the Australian context where negative FET perceptions have a negative effect on individual learners making the FET to HE transition (Barbar et al., 2015). In the Netherlands, VET learners indicated that they felt less valued in comparison to higher education students (Cedefop, 2022a). In the Irish context, learner feedback in the overall FET sector indicates learners themselves would like to see the negative societal perceptions about FET addressed particularly in the Post-Primary school sector (AONTAS, 2023). Within the literature, PLC students associate their course choice as a compromise to other education and training options which again highlights the poor societal status of FET provision (McGuinness et al., 2018).

2.1.6 Benefits of Permeability

Opening pathways between different levels of education and training, referred to as permeability, facilitates access to and participation in Lifelong Learning (European Commission, 2020; Cedefop, 2012). Across Europe, increasing permeability between FET and HE programmes has been utilised as a catalyst in improving the attractiveness of FET courses to potential learners (OECD, 2023; Cedefop, 2023).

While access to different levels of education and training are beneficial for the individual, increasing routes has wider societal benefits. In the European context, increased pathways are associated with fostering economic growth and innovation (Backes-Geller et al., 2021). At a national level, FET to HE pathways provide the opportunity to meet future skill needs and therefore contribute towards sustainable economic growth, in turn benefitting wider society (DES, 2016).

2.2 Progression from FET to HE- Student Rationale and Experience

The following section explores learners' rationale and overall experiences of the FET to HE progression experience. Furthermore, the literature aims to provide a broad overview of current progression trends in the FET to HE landscape.

2.2.1 Why people progress to Higher Education

While there are many reasons for students choosing to progress to higher education, FET learners indicate a number of motivations which include higher earning potential and a focus on further career opportunities (College Connect, 2023; National Forum, 2016). FET learners note the opportunity to act as a role model for children and the wider community as a further motivator for progression (College Connect, 2023). Individual benefits of transitioning include increasing networking capital, making new friends and the potential of engaging in an active social life (College Connect, 2023; Cree et al., 2009). FET learners also report the interest in developing an in-depth understanding of a particular subject area as an intrinsic motivation to transition to higher education (National Forum, 2016; Cree et al., 2009).

2.2.2 FET learners and HE transitions

In the available literature, students who have made the transition from FET to HE often report feeling well-prepared for the challenges of higher education (National Forum, 2016). Of most relevance, PLC students report feeling well equipped to engage in a range of assessment methods and the development of general academic competencies (Ibid, p.7). While the overall reported outcomes for FET to HE entrants is positive, this report acknowledges QQI-FET learners are a diverse cohort of students who have varied previous educational experiences which impact learner transitions to higher education differently (Catterall et al., 2014). Each year, approximately 12,000 CAO applicants record a QQI level 5 or 6 major award qualification on their application (QQI, 2024). The most prevalent QQI level 5 major award recorded on CAO applications is Nursing followed by Business studies and software development (QQI, 2024). For the academic year 2023/2024, 41.9% of CAO applicants received 8 distinctions, the highest academic attainment possible for a QQI level 5 or 6 major award (Ibid.).

The literature concerning QQI-FET to HE transitions in the Irish context indicates that introducing FET learners to university supports before or at an early stage of HE progression is central to easing the transition journey (National Forum, 2016). Students' experiences of the transition show learners have different experiences of induction which impact their transitional success (Ibid, p.16). Central to ensuring a consistent approach and facilitating smooth transitions is communication between HE and FET providers. As outlined by Murphy et al. many of the perceived barriers around progression from FET to HE can be demystified through information and experiential interventions (2023). Pre-transition information on course content, academic expectations and available HE institutional supports are essential in supporting the demystification of HE (National Forum, 2016, p.18). In a recent AONTAS learner voice forum, FET learners highlighted the need for better communication between FET and HEI institutions to develop smoother transitions (AONTAS, 2024). AONTAS has also called for the development and implementation of a transitions model to support and increase transitions across different levels of the tertiary education and training sector (2023a).

2.3 Challenges when transitioning to Higher Education

The following section highlights the challenges learners encounter when transitioning from FET to HE. The literature draws upon studies which explore students' preconceptions of HE engagement and post-transition experiences. In addition, studies which examine transitions and HE first year

undergraduate experiences within the discipline fields of Computer Science are drawn upon where possible. The literature aims to capture different elements of the student experience which include economic challenges, access and quality of guidance and information, teaching, learning and assessment experiences, and cultural experiences of higher education.

2.3.1 Financial Implications

Throughout the literature, the biggest challenge for overall student engagement in third level education not just within the FET student cohort concerns issues related to finance. Recent data shows 33% of the overall student population are experiencing serious to very serious financial difficulties (HEA, 2023, p.7). The largest expense associated with engaging in education is accommodation costs accounting for over 35% of overall expenses (Ibid). Other research into non-completion of studies indicates financial difficulties are a common contributing factor to college drop-out (National Forum, 2015a). A report published by the RIA (2021) found that even students in receipt of a SUSI grant found paying for college a challenge. FET learners outlined the fee thresholds under the grant as a challenge, particularly in families where older siblings may be working (College Connect, 2023, p.10).

While the cost-of-living crisis is impacting the student cohort as a whole, the literature suggests financial implications of engaging in third level education negatively impact FET learners' decisions to transition to higher education (College Connect, 2023; Murphy et al., 2023; INDECON, 2022; RIA, 2021; INDECON, 2019; McGuinness et al., 2018; National Forum, 2016). Guidance counsellors working in FET report financial queries about further study as the most asked questions from learners who are considering further education prospects (INDECON, 2019).

A recent review of the student grant scheme highlights the difference in cost in relation to FET and HE participation. The average cost of attending HE is estimated at €1,229 per month. This figure is approximately 10% higher than the cost of FET engagement (INDECON, 2022, p.17). Furthermore, the grant scheme has been criticised for not keeping in line with inflation rates and not covering part time programmes of study (RIA, 2021).

Research indicates FET learners with caring and family responsibilities are concerned about the financial pressures of attending third level while having to support family members (College Connect, 2023). Students who have made the transition to higher education outline the hidden or indirect costs

of attending third level such as food and travel expenses as having a negative impact on their college experiences (National Forum, 2016). Financial challenges associated with childcare provision and travel costs featured in a recent FET learner voice forum conducted by AONTAS (AONTAS, 2023; AONTAS, 2022). The financial implications of failing modules in university have also been highlighted as a rationale to cheat in academic assessments (QQI, 2023).

Available literature on FET learners' perceptions of HE highlights a gap in funding knowledge (College Connect, 2023). Findings indicate students are not aware of the full suite of potential available funding for third level students including the SUSI grant, student assistant fund and the 1916 bursary (Ibid.)

2.3.2 Career Guidance Provision in FET

Career guidance within the FET sector is underpinned by the Further Education and Training strategy 2014-2019. Under the vision for the sector, everyone who engages with FET will have access to high quality career guidance (SOLAS, 2014). Career guidance within FET provision has been characterised as inconsistent and varied across the sector (Rami et al., 2016; SOLAS, 2014). At present, guidance within FET comes under different provisions. As detailed by McKenzie et al., current PLC guidance provision has developed from post-primary educational settings (2021). Career guidance provision within PLC settings is allocated on the same ratio-based model as the post-primary school sector. A review of PLC provision in 2018 indicated 93% of PLC colleges offered guidance counselling provision (McGuinness et al., 2018, p.24).

McGuinness et al. found that even when career guidance is available within FET colleges, the service is not always well utilised (2018). Gaps in PLC provision and engagement are significant given that inaccessibility and disengagement may be negatively impacting progression pathways for PLC students, particularly those who do not have access to information and guidance outside of college.

To increase transitions from FET to HE, information on available pathways from PLC to higher education should be provided at post-primary school level. According to McGuinness et al. (2018) it is important to note that career guidance training did not include information about available education and training opportunities in the FET sector until the late 2010s. For this reason, there may be knowledge gaps around the PLC to HE

transition process within post-primary guidance cohorts. The potential knowledge gap and continual evolution of pathways require guidance counsellors to have access to up-to-date information about progression routes. The necessity to improve post-secondary school information about available pathways within the FET sector is also recognised within the FET strategy (SOLAS, 2020). In the context of post-primary school students, research indicates students are more likely to begin considering post school options during the Junior Cycle programme (INDECON, 2019). In contrast to this finding, most students do not receive information about post-school options until over the age of 16 (Ibid.). In the FET setting context, Murphy et al. (2023) found a lack of awareness and information on available routes from FET to HE as a barrier to progression.

While there is little research available on FET students' experiences of career guidance for the purpose of HE transitions and though this research has been unable to capture this experience, data collected by AONTAS in the wider context shows learners who engage with the service regard the support as an invaluable resource in helping them plan their next educational steps (AONTAS, 2023).

2.3.3 Sense of belonging

Developing a sense of belonging as a student in higher education is associated with increased attrition rates, higher motivation to study and increased self-confidence (Pedler et al., 2022; O'Keeffe, 2013). Within the Irish context, the National Access Plan refers to the significance of ensuring all students have a sense of belonging within higher education (HEA, 2022). Research shows students with a family history of third level attendance have a stronger sense of belonging in university (Erskine et al., 2023; O'Shea et al., 2018). Furthermore, developing a sense of belonging is increasingly important for learners considered at risk of dropping out of their studies (O'Keeffe, 2013). Given the rich diversity of the FET learner cohort, it is important to consider that a parent's educational attainment may vary significantly.

Studies in the area of students' transition experiences from FET to HE found students have TIt excluded and judged from the HE student cohort due to their QQI-FET educational background (Myhill et al., 2019). These findings highlight the negative impact a poor societal view of FET can have on students. As outlined by O'Farrell (2019), developing a sense of belonging for students within HE can be facilitated through liaising with FET institutions to support or ease student transitions.

Another factor influencing student's sense of belonging is the impact of space and layout. Many students who previously studied within an FET College setting are used to smaller classrooms and campuses. When examining FET students transitions across a range of disciplines, Cree et al. (2009) found the overall size and scale of institutions and learning environments were daunting for FET learners. FET learners in pre-entry reflections also highlight the size of university campuses as an intimidating aspect of FET to HE transition (College Connect, 2023). Breeze et al. (2018) found a lack of awareness of institutional layout contributed negatively to building connections and belonging to the physical space of a college institution.

Research also points out that students who have work or responsibility commitments outside of college are more likely to have less attachment and therefore a lower sense of belonging in university (O'Keeffe, 2013). Considering some QQI-FET learners may spend less time on campus due to other life commitments, creating positive student-tutor relations is central to supporting student belonging (O'Donnell et al., 2018).

2.3.4 Student tutor relations- a change in dynamic

There appears to be a marked difference in the quality and accessibility of tutor-student relations between FET and HE student experiences. Drawing from students who have travelled the FET to HE pathway it would appear the FET setting facilitates more personable tutor-student relations (Myhill et al., 2019).

A consistent characteristic of the FET landscape from the student perspective is the positive student-tutor relationship dynamic (AONTAS, 2023; College Connect 2023; AONTAS, 2022). The FET learner voice forum characterises FET tutors as 'attentive and patient' and tutors have been linked to creating learning environments that are equal, respectful and open (AONTAS, 2022, p.14; AONTAS, 2020). The impact of the positive student tutor relations within the FET setting has also been associated with improving learners' self-confidence and building self-efficacy which has a positive effect on HE transition experience (AONTAS; 2023; National Forum, 2016). Research on students' motivations to progress from FET to HE shows the positive tutor influence as a significant influence in the decision-making process (INDECON, 2019).

Within the context of higher education, student tutor relations have been associated with impacting student learning behaviours, student attrition and

overall student experience of higher education (Tormey, 2021). In the Irish context of ICT first year undergraduate programmes, one study found tutor-student relationships were more impactful than course content on student's learning behaviours and engagement (Hennessy et al., 2023). Students who have made the transition from FET to HE are attuned to the changes in tutor-student relations. In one study, students described the tutor student relationships in HE as distant (Myhill et al., 2019). Other research in the Irish context suggests undergraduate students think learning experiences with kind and caring staff who have good communication skills can increase student success in higher education (O'Farrell, 2019).

2.3.5 Assessment and Feedback experiences

Central to supporting QQI-FET to HE student transitions is the development of increased confidence and self-efficacy which are outcomes often associated with FET settings (AONTAS, 2022). These attributes are of most importance in improving student confidence with different assessment approaches and study skills (National Forum, 2016). Of most significance, FET learners often report being well prepared for the variation of assessment approaches adopted in higher education (Myhill et al., 2019; National Forum, 2016). While the literature highlights an overall positive FET assessment preparation, engaging in group work has been identified as a challenging component of continuous assessment for FET learners (QQI, 2023) and FET learners find group work particularly challenging when working with traditional Leaving Certificate students who often have different learning approaches (National Forum, 2016). Although the literature suggests FET students have broad exposure to different assessment modes, one study indicates assessment procedures in FET can sometimes lack objectivity and inhibit the development of independent approaches to learning (Cree et al., 2009).

Available literature on the student experience of feedback highlights a marked difference between FET and HE settings. Comparative research shows FET learners often receive timely, well-informed feedback in comparison to HE student experiences (QQI, 2023, p.5). FET tutors also often provide opportunities to discuss assessment briefs and requirements in class (Ibid.). Data captured through the HE Student survey shows the lowest satisfaction score in relation to the teaching and learning experience was accessing feedback for ongoing work and post-assessment (Student Survey 2023; Student Survey 2022). A further contrasting point between FET and HE experience is the fact that FET learners report more flexibility in relation to formative assessment where the HE student experience can

be one of institutional inflexibility (QQI, 2023). Given the positive correlation between timely, comprehensive feedback and building non-traditional student's confidence in the HE learning environment, these findings are of significance (Fleming et al., 2017). In addition, given the HE student experience presented in this report includes non-specific FET entrant cohorts, improving access and quality of feedback could potentially benefit the wider HE student body.

2.3.6 Mathematics challenges

Mathematics anxiety amongst third level students has been found to negatively impact students' experience of transitioning to university regardless of previous educational background (Hennessy et al., 2023). Research specific to the FET to HE context indicates mathematics expectations in HE can be a particular challenge for QQI-FET entrant learners (Katartzi et al., 2020; Myhill et al., 2019; National Forum, 2016; Catterall et al., 2024).

One study within the Irish context of first year computing students found that even when students are aware of available mathematics learning support, asking for help can prove challenging (Hennessy et al., 2023). This phenomenon appears to be more prevalent among non-mature students (ibid.). Moreover, ICT students with low mathematics confidence and those who have little pre-entry mathematics and analytics curriculum experience are more likely to drop out of their undergraduate studies (National Forum, 2015).

Similarities among Leaving Certificate and QQI-FET entrants to HE programmes indicate an unpreparedness for the standard of mathematics required at third level (National Forum, 2016; National Forum, 2015a). Of most relevance, the National Forum survey found FET participants undertaking Business and Economics programmes found the mathematics components particularly challenging (National Forum, 2016). Interestingly, FET students studying mathematics and computer-based PLC programmes have the highest objective of progressing to higher education in comparison to students studying within other domains of learning (INDECON, 2019).

Regardless of progression demands in the area of ICT students, QQI-FET to HE pathways in the areas of STEM education have been challenging to establish. While pathways from QQI-FET to HE in ICT disciplines are beginning to emerge, entry requirements are often specific to a number of QQI major awards.

As outlined by Rami et al. (2016) the co-development of a QQI level 5 mathematics module between FET and HE providers has provided a bridge in developing a module which supports the student transition. Other research indicates student transitions benefit greatly from strong content links between PLC and HE programmes (National Forum, 2016).

It is also worth noting that research in the areas of mathematics and career guidance has found students who have access to one-to-one career guidance have improved Mathematics achievement outcomes (Cedefop et al., 2021; Kashefpakdel et al., 2017). As highlighted previously, not all students studying at PLC level have access to one-to-one guidance support and the relationship between mathematics and Guidance in the context of FET is worth further investigation (McGuinness et al., 2018).

2.4 Summary and Conclusion

The literature aimed to provide an overview of the FET to HE landscape in which this study is set. In addition, this section provides an insight into current PLC to HE trends and highlights the societal perceptions of FET as a sector from the learner's perspective. The current barriers of FET to HE progression for the student cohort have been presented and the main academic and non-academic differences of FET to HE have been explored. This report outlines significant policy and governance developments which have led to increased entry routes to higher education for QQI-FET entrants. While pathways from FET to HE continue to expand, there remain systemic and administrative barriers which negatively impact the further development of increased permeability such as the unavailability of equitable access routes for learners applying to HE on the grounds of QQI qualifications.

Drawing on available literature within the context of the Irish Tertiary Education landscape, financial implications of HE engagement is the greatest barrier to HE participation for QQI-FET learners. In addition to financial implications, inconsistent career guidance provision across the FET sector could be negatively impacting FET to HE transitions.

QQI-FET learners who do make the transition to higher education recognise differences in academic culture and expectations. The level of mathematics competencies required in an undergraduate qualification is often a challenge for QQI-FET entrants. This phenomenon is not exclusive to QQI-FET entrants with similar academic experiences noted in the wider first year undergraduate student cohort. Students entering HE following the completion of a QQI-FET qualification experience a change in student-tutor

dynamic and a different approach to assessment and feedback. In addition, the literature shows negative societal perceptions of FET can negatively impact QQI-FET university entrants, which sometimes results in learners feeling like they don't belong in higher education.

3 Methodology

The following section outlines the research team's approaches to student recruitment and data collection. Insights from student engagement at the recruitment phase are discussed and unforeseen circumstances which impacted data collection are outlined.

3.1 Mixed Methods Approach

The research team planned to implement a mixed-methods approach to capturing the student experience of transitions from FET to DCU. The mixed method approach was selected to ensure rounded and balanced findings. Available quantitative data were analysed with the aim of identifying any potential progression trends and gaining insight into students' academic performance particularly within the areas of mathematics and practical-based modules such as Computer programming. The research team intended to gather primary qualitative data from first year undergraduate student cohorts by conducting one to one interviews.

Due to unforeseen circumstances, there were significant issues and barriers in collecting qualitative data. Due to the collection of limited qualitative data, the quantitative data and supplementary research and literature form the basis of the key findings within this report.

3.1.1 Interview Process

One to one interviews using a semi-structured approach were the intended primary data collection method (Appendix A). This approach was chosen to ensure participants had the opportunity to explore and discuss ideas they felt were relevant to their journey of transitioning from FET to DCU. Given the interview process aimed to capture the student experience which spanned over a twelve-month period the team used word cues to support participants to recall and reflect on their academic journey to date (Appendix B).

Interview questions were piloted with a cohort of students who had experience progressing from further education to higher education. In total, five participants took part in the sample. As mentioned above, there were significant issues and barriers in collecting qualitative data. This resulted in the team conducting only one student interview.

3.1.2 Qualitative Sample Size

The overall potential qualitative data sample size consisted of 22 potential participants who entered DCU in the academic year 2022/2023. At the time of participant recruitment, the intended cohort were in their second academic year of DC115 Accounting and Finance and DC121 Computer Science. Qualitative interviews were designed to capture the first-year student experience as a DCU student. After numerous outreach attempts, which are detailed below, the team changed focus to capture the first-year student cohort experience for those who entered DC115 Accounting and Finance and DC121 Computer Science in the academic year 2023/2024. The change in academic cohort resulted in a potential sample size of 23 students.

In the early stages of the research, it became apparent that one of the first-year undergraduate cohorts for the academic year 2023/2024 could not be contacted by the research team. This barrier to data collection resulted in the potential sample size being reduced from 23 to 8. After numerous attempts to contact the first-year cohort of eight potential participants one student took part in a qualitative interview.

3.2 Recruitment approach

The first year QQI-FET cohort for 2023/2023 were initially contacted via email at the end of Semester two in May 2023. This approach was facilitated through the programme chairs who disseminated the email from the research team to both Accounting and Finance and Computer Science first year undergraduate students. The initial outreach approach yielded no response. Potential contributing factors to the lack of engagement include poor timing in relation to end-of-year exams/assessments and large volumes of emails to student DCU email accounts. A second outreach attempt was implemented in September 2023 which targeted 2022/2023 first year entrants. Members of the research team provided a ten-minute presentation on the project to Accounting and Finance students (Appendix C). To ensure confidentiality among students a sign-up flyer (Appendix D) was circulated during the session which included a google forms register of interest application and the research teams contact details (Appendix E). A follow-up video was circulated via the student loop page.

Following the presentation, one participant completed the registration form. Unfortunately, follow up communication with the potential participant showed they had not entered DCU via a QQI Further Education and Training Route. After several attempts at recruiting students for interview, a decision

was made to also include a small financial gift voucher to compensate students for loss of earnings given the current cost of living crisis and financial barriers to HE participation highlighted in the literature review.

At the beginning of 2024 the research team decided to redeploy the presentation and information video recruitment approach with the first year Accounting and Finance cohort of 2023/2024. One participant who fitted the criteria signed up for the study and took part in a qualitative interview in Spring 2024. Whilst there were some interesting observations emerging from this interview, findings are too limited to draw inference from it.

3.2.1 Insights from student engagement

The limited interaction between students and the research team highlighted the lack of clarity some students may encounter regarding prior educational attainment and entry route. During the register of interest phase two students from the selected cohort signed up to take part in the study. Upon further correspondence with the research team, it became apparent these students were unsure as to which qualifications they had previously obtained and which entry route they had availed of to enter their current programme. The uncertainty regarding previous qualifications could be impacted by changes in the naming of qualifications at QQI level which have occurred in the last decade. Uncertainty around the entry route may indicate this piece of information is insignificant to students on their journey to obtaining entry. In addition, some students may have multiple potential entry route options in the one academic year such as mature student and FET entrant.

Following student recruitment attempts with the selected DC115 and DC121 cohorts, three students from the Business School outside of the selected sample groups signed up through the register of interest form. All three students were aware they had previously completed a QQI level 5 qualification prior to entering DCU. The interest generated may have been from flyers left in the lecture hall or perhaps from students on the Accounting and Finance programme sharing the information with other cohorts. The three students were contacted via email to inform them they did not meet the criteria to engage in the study. Irrespective of how the information was circulated, this finding indicates there are DCU students who have come from a PLC college interested in sharing their experiences.

3.3 Summary and Conclusion

This section has outlined the methodological approaches which were adopted in this study. Challenges with student recruitment including a reduction in the potential sample size were discussed and the overall qualitative data participation of one student is highlighted. While there were challenges in obtaining qualitative data, student engagement during outreach presentations, email correspondence with students and during the one qualitative interview highlights potential gaps in information and guidance knowledge.

4 Quantitative Data Analysis

The following section highlights the key findings derived from quantitative data made available through the QIO (Quality and Institutional Insight Office) in DCU. As outlined in the previous chapter, there were significant challenges in obtaining primary qualitative data. As a result, data analysis in this report focuses on key findings on access, progression and academic performance identified in the available quantitative data specific to QQI-FET undergraduate first year students on DC115 and DC121 programmes.

4.1 Available data

The research team received ethical approval to access available participation and academic grading information specific to QQI-FET entrants on both Accounting and Finance DC115 and Computer Science DC121 programmes. Entry routes from FET to DC115 have been established for a number of years. For this reason, quantitative data spanning five years was available for analysis. In comparison, 2022/2023 was the first year QQI-FET entrants were offered places on the Computer Science programme. Therefore, limited data is available on student access and academic achievement for the DC121 FET entrant cohort.

4.1.1 DCU programme offers to QQI-FET learners

Available data indicates QQI-FET learners who are offered a place on DC 115 and DC121 are highly likely to accept their place on their chosen programme of study. In total the overall sample indicates 88% of students over five academic years from 2019/2020-2023/2024 accepted their place on the selected programmes (Appendix F). Analysing the data on an annual basis for DC115 and DC121 entrants collectively highlights a 100% acceptance rate in three of the past five academic years including 2023/2024, 2020/2021 and 2019/2020. This finding is in contradiction to previous larger comparative studies which indicate QQI-FET applicants are less likely to accept offers in higher education institutions (DES, 2020).

4.1.2 Acceptance Rates of QQI-FET Entrants

In total, 74 QQI-FET applicants have gained entry to Accounting and Finance (DC115) and Computer Science (DC121) undergraduate programmes through a QQI-FET qualification pathway since 2019. As previously stated, the QQI-FET entry pathway to Computer Science is a relatively new progression route in the FET to DCU context.

While acceptance rates on the DC121 programme continue to increase there has been more fluctuation in FET student acceptance on DC115 with a decrease in accepted places in 2023/2024. However, collectively the sample shows the number of QQI-FET applicants accepting places on the selected programmes has continued to increase on an annual basis. This finding captures DCU's commitment to widening participation and shows changes in admission criteria are effective in attracting FET learners.

4.1.3 QQI-FET Student Overall Retention Rates

The available data on student retention within the parameters of this study were limited to information on first year undergraduate students enrolled on their respective programmes in the March of semester two. The collective student retention rate until March of semester two of the entire sample including DC115 students from 2019/2020 to 2023/2024 and DC121 students for 2022/2023 and 2023/2024 is 87%.

4.1.4 DC115 Accounting and Finance

Referring specifically to the QQI-FET Accounting and Finance cohort, data shows a collective retention rate from registration to semester two of 81.8%. This retention rate is the collective sample of first year students who entered D115 through the QQI-FET route from 2019/2020 to 2023/2024. It is worth noting retention rates specific to individual academic years are lowest during the periods of study which were most impacted by the Covid 19 pandemic, notably 2019/2020 and 2020/2021 (Appendix G).

4.1.5 DC121 Computer Science

Although available data for the Computer Science QQI-FET entrant cohort is limited to two years, the collective overall retention rate from September to March for the academic years 2022/2023 and 2023/2024 is 96.6% (Appendix H). This represents a total drop out of one student in the transition from semester one to semester two. This finding correlates with previous larger scale studies which show students who completed a Post-Leaving Certificate programme prior to entering higher education have a high rate of retention during year one of their undergraduate studies (DES, 2020, p.22).

4.2 Previous Educational Attainment

Available data on QQI-FET entrant's academic outcomes and prior institutional attendance before entering DCU was extremely limited.

Information on previously obtained major QQI awards and achieved grades used to gain entry to DCU through the QQI-FET route was not available. Furthermore, information on previously attended education and training institutions was limited to which Post Primary schools students attended. Post Primary school attendance information was only available where a QQI-FET cohort included this information on their CAO application. As a result, there is no information about which QQI qualifications were used to gain entry to DCU or which FET College students attended. The lack of available data reduces the ability to capture the student journey from FET to DCU. However, the available information provides an insight into which post-primary schools QQI-FET entrants attended.

In total, 60 out of 74 QQI-FET entrants recorded sitting a Leaving Certificate Examination within the collective DC121 and DC115 cohort from 2019/2020 to 2023/2024. As part of the CAO application, it is not compulsory for QQI-FET entrants to record Leaving Certificate results. It is also possible that, given the diverse cohort within the sample, some of the QQI-FET entrants sat school examinations outside of the state. There is also a likelihood that some of the applicants may not have sat the Leaving Certificate examination, therefore the QQI-FET route provided a basis for entry outside of the traditional SEC entry pathway.

4.2.1 Patterns of Progression

The following section explores findings within the available quantitative data that are specific to previous educational attainment of QQI-FET entrants prior to becoming DCU first year undergraduate students. In addition, patterns of progression are discussed in the context of proficient guidance and local knowledge. Lastly, gender progression trends in the area of STEM are highlighted within the context of this study.

4.2.2 DEIS School Attendance

Available quantitative data from DCU QIIO shows 26.6% of QQI-FET entrants who included Leaving Certificate qualifications on their CAO application attended a DEIS school prior to entering Further Education and Training. This finding may underline previous progression trends which indicate students progressing from FET to HE are more likely to have sat the Leaving Certificate in non-DEIS post-primary school. In line with available literature which indicates financial barriers are a challenge for FET learners in progressing to HE it is important to note students who attend DEIS schools have a higher prevalence rate of experiencing socio-

economic disadvantage than those attending non-DEIS schools (Neils et al., 2021). This finding also supports previous research in the area of transitions which indicates that students who have experienced socio-economic challenges are less likely to progress onto higher education after completing a PLC programme (Mc Coy et al., 2014).

4.2.3 Trends in Post-Primary Schools to PLC to HE Progression

In total, the overall sample cohort of DC115 and DC121 students entering DCU via a QQI-FET entry route for the academic years 2019/2020 to 2023/2024 indicates 60 students within the combined cohort of 74 entrants recorded sitting a Leaving Certificate Examination. The 60 students who recorded a post-primary school or institute on their CAO attended 45 different post-primary settings. All of the post-primary schools recorded are within the Dublin, Eastern Midlands and Ulster Regions (Appendix I). 58% of students who record a post-primary school setting on their CAO form attended school in Eastern Midlands and Ulster Regions. 40% of students attended school in Dublin and County Dublin areas. 2% of students' school attendance record is unknown. This information is significant in understanding progression patterns. Please refer to Appendix I for more information.

4.2.4 Potential trends in School Guidance and Local Knowledge

23 students out of the sample population of 60 undergraduate DC115 and DC121 QQI-FET entrants who recorded sitting a Leaving Certificate examination on their CAO application attended nine post-primary schools. Interestingly, 13 students or 21% of the overall DC115 and DC121 QQI-FET student cohort had attended four post-primary education schools and institution settings. This finding potentially indicates school guidance or local knowledge may be an influential factor in understanding transitions from PLC to higher education.

4.2.5 Gender Trends in Computer Science

QQI-FET entrants to the Computer Science undergraduate programme are predominantly male (Appendix J). This gender trend reflects the national and international participation in STEM education programmes within further and higher education. A recent OECD report indicates less than one quarter of entrants to STEM based tertiary education programmes are

female (OECD, 2023). From a national perspective, data from 2021/22 shows 21% of students engaging in third level ICT programmes are female and 79% male (HEA, 2023, p.3). In addition, the findings reflect patterns in FET programmes with males accounting for 76% of the cohort who received a QQI level 5 qualification in ICT in 2024 (QQI, 2024).

While the sample is small it is worth noting female students have a higher acceptance rate onto the programme in comparison to their male counterparts.

4.3 Academic Outcomes- Year One performance

This report provides insight into QQI-FET entrants academic performance outcomes for year one of their undergraduate studies as a DCU student. To gain insight into any potential areas of challenge and achievement for QQI-FET entrants overall academic annual performance outcomes and individual modules outcomes which cover different subject areas and assessment methods are included in this report. This information was provided by the Quality and Institutional Insight Office (QIIO) in DCU.

In consultation with DCU staff members and drawing on available literature individual modules in mathematics, practical-based learning and critical thinking development modules were selected. Individual academic module outcomes were analysed using average precision marks for the chosen subjects. In accordance with DCU Marks and Standards regulations, the average precision mark is 'normally the overall weighted average for the first full presentation of marks for an academic session' (2020, p.24). To gain insight into student academic performance in the wider context of the DCU student cohort, this report provides comparative analysis of outcomes between QQI-FET, Standard CAO or traditional Leaving Certificate entrants, and other route cohorts such as HEAR, DARE and Sport scholarships students.

4.3.1 Overall Annual Academic performance

The following section outlines the annual overall academic performance outcomes for first year QQI-FET undergraduate students within DC121 and DC115 undergraduate programs. Available APM marks from QIIO DCU office form the basis of all presented academic outcome data. These outcomes are limited to the 2022/2023 academic year for the DC121 program. Three academic year outcomes for DC115 are included which span academic years 2020/2021, 2021/2022 and 2022/2023.

4.3.2 DC121 Computer Science

Due to the time of data collection, available data on overall average performance marks is limited to the academic year 2022/2023. The APM for QQI-FET entrants for 2022/2023 is 46.29 (Appendix K). In academic grading, QQI-FET entrants overall academic performance for year one is a H3 grade. The overall APM for standard Leaving Certificate entrants is 53.34. Other route entrants which include HEAR and DARE students have an annual APM of 57.28.

4.3.3 DC115 Accounting and Finance

Available data on academic outcomes across three academic years 2020/2021 to 2022/2023 shows QQI-FET entrants in year one of Accounting and Finance undergraduate programme have an overall APM mark ranging between 51.11 and 55.78 (Appendix L). In terms of academic achievement, this finding indicates the overall average grade for year one QQI-FET entrants on DC115 is a 2.2. The average academic grade for standard CAO entrants is a 2.1. Students entering DCU through other routes such as HEAR and DARE have an overall average year one grade ranging between 2.1 and 2.2. To understand differences in academic performance the following section focuses on single module based outcomes.

4.4 Module specific analysis

This section highlights specific module academic performance outcomes of first year QQI-FET entrant undergraduate students on the selected programmes DC115 and DC121. To develop an understanding of academic performance across a range of subject disciplines and assessment methods the research team explored individual module outcomes.

4.4.1 DC121 Computer Science Module outcomes

The following DC121 individual modules are presented in this report: CA116 Computer Programming One; CA117 Computer Programming Two; MS134 Mathematics One; MS135 Mathematics Two and CA172 Problem Solving, Creativity and Critical Thinking. Given the available limited data of QQI-FET entrants onto the Computer Science programme this report focuses on available academic performance of 2022/2023 and 2023/2024.

4.4.2 Laboratory-based modules

The data included in this report indicates QQI-FET learners achieve a lower APM in laboratory-based modules in comparison to students who entered DCU through different routes. Although it is challenging to draw conclusions without primary data, the available literature indicates QQI-FET entrants may have less time available to spend on campus due to potential caring responsibilities and other life commitments such as employment (College Connect, 2023). The available literature from which this hypothesis is established is drawn from recent research in the Irish context which explored PLC learners' views on progression to HE (Ibid.). Drawing from the literature, the potential reduced time available to spend on campus may be negatively impacting QQI-FET entrants' opportunities to engage with learning in a laboratory-based setting.

4.4.3 CA116 Computer Programming One

Computer Programming One is a ten-credit module which takes place in year one, semester one. According to the module descriptor, assessment is 60% laboratory-based continuous assessment and 40% examination. As indicated in the descriptor, the module requires a significant amount of supervised laboratory work (DCU, 2024).

The information in the table below highlights academic outcomes in the form of APM achievement between QQI-FET learners, Other routes and Standard CAO students. The data shows an achievement gap difference of 22.56 marks between QQI-FET and Standard CAO students. The comparative difference in academic performance is much smaller when comparing QQI-FET entrants to Other Route students with a difference of 7.02 marks. Focusing specifically on Further Education achievements, 58.82% of the 2023/2024 cohort passed the module.

Year	FE Entrants	Other Routes	Standard CAO	FE Entrant Pass Rate
2023/2024	37.12	44.14	59.68	58.82%

Fig 1. Average precision mark of DC121 module CA116 in the academic year 2023/2024

4.4.4 CA117 Computer Programming Two

Computer Programming Two is a ten-credit module which takes place in year one semester two. The assessment is 50% continuous assessment in the form of laboratory exams and 50% examination (DCU, 2024a).

As indicated in the table below, QQI-FET entrants record a lower APM achievement in comparison to other entrant routes and standard CAO students. The APM differentiation between standard CAO and QQI-FET entrants is 19 marks. There is an 8.3 marks differentiation between QQI-FET students and Other route entrants. In total, 26.09% of the Further Education route students passed the module.

Year	FE Entrants	Other Routes	Standard CAO	FE Entrant Pass Rate
2022/2023	33.93	42.24	52.93	26.09%

Fig 2. Average precision mark & FE entrant cohort pass rate DC121 module code CA117 in the academic year 2023/2023

4.4.5 Mathematics modules

QQI-FET entrants on DC121 have a lower APM average in comparison to students entering through the standard Leaving Certificate and other routes such as HEAR and DARE. Research in the context of FET to HE transitions indicates mathematics modules can prove challenging for FET learners (Katartzi et al., 2020; Myhill et al., 2019; National Forum, 2016).

4.4.6 MS134 IT Mathematics One

Mathematics One is a five-credit module. The assessment is 80% examination and 20% continuous assessment. Continuous assessment takes the form of in-class tests spread throughout the module. The module focuses on algebraic and logical skills development (DCU, 2024b).

The available data, which spans two years, indicates QQI-FET entrants have a lower APM achievement in comparison to Other cohorts. However, it is worth noting in the academic year 2023/2024 the APM differentiation between QQI-FET entrants and other routes is less than 1 mark at 0.48. There is also a 12.18 mark increase when comparing 2022/23 and 2023/23 Further Education entrants. The overall pass rate of QQI-FET entrants on attempt one of MS134 was 31.82% in 2022/2023. The QQI-FET cohort pass rate increased to 50% in 2023/2024.

Year	FET Entrants	Other Routes	Standard CAO	FET Entrant
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				Pass Rate
2022/2023	34.32	49.25	59.68	31.82%
2023/2024	46.50	46.98	59.49	50%

Fig 3. Average precision mark & FET entrant cohort pass rate DC121 module code MS134 in the academic years 2022/23 & 2023/24

4.4.7 MS135 IT Mathematics Two

Mathematics Two is a five-credit module. 20% of the overall grade is given to continuous assessment with the remaining 80% on final assessment (DCU, 2024c). The module focuses on developing algebraic and logical skills.

Available data shows students in the QQI-FET entrant cohort have a lower average APM in comparison to students entering from Leaving Certificate and other routes. The average precision mark and pass rate are lower in comparison to outcomes in Mathematics One. The overall pass rate for attempt one of MS135 is 26.09%. The available data on this module is limited to one year of outcomes.

Year	FET Entrants	Other Routes	Standard CAO	FET Entrant Pass Rate
2022/2023	25.60	47.63	56.86	26.09%

Fig 4. Average precision mark & FET entrant cohort pass rate DC121 module code MS135 in the academic year 2022/23

4.4.8 CA172 Problem Solving, Creativity and Critical Thinking

This is a five-credit module which aims to support problem solving, creativity, and critical thinking in both individual and group work approaches (DCU, 2024d). Assessment for this module is 100% continuous with 50% of the overall module mark dedicated to portfolio creation.

In the available data across two academic years the QQI-FET entrant cohort achieved a higher APM in comparison to students entering from other routes. Furthermore, the APM differentiation between QQI-FET students

and standard Leaving Certificate entrants is 4.18 for the academic year 2022/23 and less than 2.41 in the academic year 2023/2024. The overall pass rate for 2022/23 students is 75%. This figure increases to 86.5% in 2023/2024.

Year	FET Route	Other Routes	Standard CAO	FET Entrant Pass Rate
2022/2023	52.86	51.46	57.04	75%
2023/2024	59.06	56	61.67	87.5%

Fig 5. Average precision mark & FET entrant cohort pass rate DC121 module code CA172 in the academic years 2022/23 & 2023/24

4.4.9 Comparing module outcomes in Computer Science

The above information shows QQI-FET entrants have a lower APM in comparison to students who entered DCU via different routes when comparing mathematics based and practical, laboratory-based modules. In contrast, the QQI-FET entrants cohort have higher APM outcomes in module CA172 Problem Solving, Creativity and Critical thinking. While the quantitative data is limited to providing information on academic outcomes, literature findings indicate the assessment and feedback approach could be an influential factor in module outcomes. Furthermore, as highlighted above, QQI-FET entrants often find mathematics specific modules challenging and potentially have less time to spend on campus for laboratory-based modules if they have caring or employment responsibilities. To fully investigate the impact of assessment methods and subject areas on academic outcomes future research should include analysis of a broader set of modules across a more expansive range of subjects.

4.5 Accounting and Finance Module Outcomes

To gain a more in-depth understanding of academic outcomes for year one QQI-FET DC115 entrant students, this report presents available information on mathematics based and critical thinking focused modules. The following module outcomes are presented in this report: MS114 Accounting Mathematics and SB102 Critical Thinking for Business. These modules were selected on the basis of literature findings and to provide a comparison of mathematics and non-mathematics based module outcomes within the accounting and finance cohort. Given QQI-FET entry routes are in existence

to the DC115 Accounting and Finance programme since the academic year 2019/2020, five years data is included in the analysis.

4.5.1 Mathematics module

Qualitative literature suggests mathematics based modules can be particularly challenging for students who have made the transition to Business and Economic modules (National Forum, 2015). Analysis of MS144 Mathematics module aligns academic outcomes with this finding.

4.5.2 MS114 Mathematics

MS114 Mathematics is a five credit module undertaken by year one students in semester one. The module focuses on various elements of mathematics including calculus, and geometry and arithmetic (DCU, 2024e). 80% of the overall grade is completed through final assessment. 20% of continuous assessment is completed through a class test. Available comparative data is limited to an APM for QQI-FET entrants and a combined APM for Other and Standard CAO students. APM outcomes of Standard CAO and other entrant cohorts are combined in line with ethical considerations.

Module outcomes show QQI-FET students have a lower APM and pass rate over a five year period in comparison to students entering DCU from different routes. In relation to QQI-FET entrants outcomes there is a progressive gradual annual increase of academic achievement for each successive first year cohort with the exception of 2022/2023. Due to the lack of qualitative data it is not possible to determine the cause of this anomaly. Furthermore, with the exception of 2022/2023 all APMs in the QQI-FET entrant cohort were above the pass rate of 40 marks.

Academic Year	FET Entrant APM	FET Entrant Pass Rate	Standard CAO & Other routes APM	Standard CAO & Other routes Pass Rate
2019/2020	40.8	50%	60.39	89.47%
2020/2021	42	50%	57.54	78.42%
2021/2022	47.89	66.67%	68.60	89.92%
2022/2023	39.27	66.67%	71.38	89.38%
2023/2024	53.38	87.5%	69.64	94.64%

Fig 6. APM outcomes of first year DC115 undergraduate students on Module MS114 Mathematics

4.5.3 SB102 Critical Thinking for Business

SB102 is a five credit module which aims to support first year undergraduate students critical thinking skills. The module is 100% continuous assessment based and includes a range of activities across the module including group work, reflections and a quiz.

Academic outcomes in this module indicate QQI-FET entrants have a 100% overall pass rate with the exception of the academic year 2020/21. When comparing academic outcomes between QQI-FET and non QQI-FET entrants the comparison in academic outcome is below 2.73 marks in three of the four academic years. Furthermore, the QQI-FET entrant students have a higher pass rate in comparison to other cohorts of students in three of the four academic years.

Academic Year	FET Entrant APM	FET Entrant Pass Rate	Standard CAO & Other Routes APM	Standard CAO & Other route Entrant Pass Rate
2019/2020	67	100%	69.73	100%
2020/2021	52.38	75%	66.79	99.17%
2021/2022	67	100%	68.44	98.2%
2022/2023	71.57	100%	72.78	97%

Fig 7. APM outcomes of first year DC115 undergraduate students on Module SB102 Critical thinking for business

4.5.4 Comparing Mathematics and Non-Mathematics based modules

Similar to findings within the Computer Science cohort DC115 QQI-FET entrant academic module outcomes are lower in mathematics based modules when compared to other entrants. Furthermore, referring specifically to the Critical Thinking for Business module, QQI-FET entrants have the highest pass rate record in three of the four academic years. To explore whether outcome challenges are exclusive to mathematics modules further analysis of individual based modules is required.

4.5.5 Dual QQI-FET entrants' academic outcomes

Student information in relation to the accounting and finance cohort for the academic years 2019/2020 to 2021/2022 show two students who gained entry through the Further Education route also fall within the age band of potential eligibility for mature student entry. In addition, one QQI-FET entrant within the same time frame is also tagged in the available QIIO data as both a QQI-FET and Access student. Data shows 100% of QQI-FET entrants who were within the age bracket to also be considered as mature students obtained an overall Fail mark for year one of their studies. Although the sample is very small, this finding suggests repetition requirements may be more prevalent for QQI-FET entrants who are also potentially eligible for entry consideration under mature student and access categories. To fully explore if outcomes are more prevalent in students who potentially fall within multiple widening participation category bands, information on Mature and Access students who have previously attended a QQI-FET college but did not gain entry via this route would need to be accessed. Referring to available literature, a recent INDECON report found 72% of mature students had engaged in an Education and Training programme prior to entering higher education (INDECON, 2021, p.ix). Therefore, the number of mature students who completed a QQI level 5 prior to entering DCU may be much higher than those who gained entry through the specific QQI-FET route. In addition, longitudinal HEA data shows there has been an increase in non-progression rates beyond the first year of undergraduate studies within the 25-29 cohort (HEA, 2024, p.20). This is worth considering given this tentative finding.

4.6 Summary and Conclusion

This section of the report has presented retention and academic outcomes of first year QQI-FET entrants studying on programmes DC115 and DC121. Outcomes are drawn from quantitative data made available by the QIIO office in DCU. While acceptance and retention rates specific to the first year QQI-FET student cohorts show positive outcomes, the data indicates QQI-FET entrants experience academic challenges in the areas of mathematics and practical-based modules. Interestingly, in the context of first year undergraduate, DC115 QQI-FET entrants academic performance in Mathematics module MS144 shows a gradual increase in APM achievement from 2019/20 to 2023/2024. This is however with the exception of the academic year 2022/2023. Furthermore, available quantitative data indicates QQI-FET entrants who could also be considered for entry on the basis of widening participation status such as Mature student or Access students may be more likely required to repeat first year academic modules.

Quantitative data analysis and literature findings will be discussed further in the findings section of this report.

5 Key findings and Limitations

The following section outlines the key findings relating to the study of first year DCU undergraduate student experiences of the transition from FET to HE. Furthermore, research limitations which impacted the study are discussed to provide insight into the main challenges of this project. As outlined previously, due to limited qualitative data collection, the findings in this report rely heavily on available quantitative data specific to the first year undergraduate student experience of DC115 and DC121 students. Findings are further informed by national, European and international academic literature.

5.1 Key findings

Key findings in this report draw upon available quantitative and secondary qualitative data specific to the QQI-FET to HE student experience. Findings specific to potential barriers in FET to HE progression are discussed. Furthermore, the main academic performance findings specific to QQI-FET entrants to DC115 and DC121 are outlined. Deficits in information and guidance are also outlined.

5.1.1 Financial Barriers to Higher Education progression

Drawing from available qualitative secondary data in the literature review, the financial cost of participating in higher education is the most significant barrier for students considering transition from FET to HE. While research indicates the financial challenges of HE participation are not exclusive to QQI-FET entrants the literature shows there is a marked increase in financial costs between FET and HE engagement (INDECON, 2022). Available research specific to FET learner's experience suggests FET students are not always aware of available University financial supports such as the Student Assistant Fund and the 1916 Bursary. The lack of knowledge regarding financial supports could potentially negatively impact learners making the decision to progress to HE after FET.

5.1.2 Previous Education Attainment

Current data from the DCU Quality and Institutional Insights Office (QIIO) programme dashboard indicates that QQI-FET entrants who listed a post-primary school on their CAO application are more likely to have attended a non-DEIS school. This potential finding at first glance may suggest that students entering the highlighted programmes through the QQI route may not have faced the social and economic disadvantages typically associated

with attending a DEIS school. This finding aligns with previous research indicating that students from working-class backgrounds are less likely to transition from Post-Leaving Certificate (PLC) qualifications to higher education (McGuinness et al., 2018; McCoy et al., 2014). However, it is important to note that this conclusion remains preliminary and could also be attributed to the lack of 'previous school' information recorded by the applicant on their CAO QQI-FET Application.

5.1.3 Guidance and Information provision

Previous research included in the literature of this report suggests there is a lack of awareness and information on routes from FET to HE in the FET context (Murphy et al., 2023). Although it may be argued this is due to inconsistency in access availability to guidance within FET, McGuinness et al. argues even when career guidance is available within FET colleges, the service is not always utilised (2018).

Although the sample size is too small to make any definitive conclusions on the overall student experience, it is important to note the student who took part wanted to make a contribution towards the research team understanding the QQI-FET cohort entrant experience. Information gathered during this interview (however limited) does support literature findings on the broad range of inaccessibility of information and available guidance within FET settings, particularly in the area of progression to higher education (McGuinness et al., 2018; Rami et al., 2016). Below is a quote from this participant's experience of guidance and information on PLC to HE progression.

'I actually didn't realise that you could get into all the courses (referring to undergraduate programmes) that you could get in from doing the PLC. Like I couldn't believe it.'

While there have been significant changes to FET and Adult Guidance provision in the last number of years which has increased access and information on FET to HE progression, a more consistent information and guidance approach across all FET Colleges and Education and Training Boards (ETBs) could further improve access and progression in the context of FET to HE pathways.

5.1.4 Acceptance trends in QQI-FET applicants

Quantitative analysis of DCU offers and acceptances indicates QQI entrants on the two specific programmes have a high acceptance rate. This trend is

particularly evident within the Computer Science programme which has an 85.7% acceptance rate to date from QQI-FET entrants. This finding counters the trend seen in the literature which shows QQI-FET applicants acceptance rate to third level institutions are generally in the range of 50-60% (DES, 2020). This finding signifies DCU's commitment to widening participation and potentially indicates DCU is considered a welcoming and valued University from the FET learner's perspective.

5.1.5 Academic challenges

The first year QQI students have relatively low pass rates in DCU mathematics modules and practical-based modules in comparison to Standard CAO and Other Cohort (entrants such as HEAR and DARE and Sports Scholarships) entrants.

Due to the limitation of a qualitative data sample of one, the literature is relied upon to understand this phenomenon. Literature suggests mathematics modules in higher education can be particularly challenging for QQI-FET entrants (Myhill et al., 2019; National Forum for Teaching and Learning in Higher Education, 2016). Furthermore, practical-based modules which require attendance and access to laboratories for study may be more inaccessible to QQI-FET students if they have life commitments outside of third level education such as caring responsibilities and financial implications (College Connect, 2023; National Forum, 2016). Attendance records or information on access to laboratory-based settings for study purposes outside of module times could potentially offer further insight into this finding, this was not sought or obtained during the research ethics approval process.

The research also tentatively suggests QQI-FET entrants who also could be considered as mature students or fall within Access supports have a higher chance of failure in year one in comparison to those who are recorded under single QQI-FET entrants status. This finding is based on the limited data available within the parameters of the research.

5.1.6 Academic achievements

QQI-FET entrant academic achievement outside of mathematics (modules and laboratory-based modules shows QQI-FET entrants' academic performance is more evenly matched to students from the traditional CAO LC points route. Furthermore, an analysis of year-by-year academic performance shows QQI-FET entrants studying on both DC121 and DC115

have higher APM achievements in critical thinking-based modules in comparison to other entry route student cohorts. Furthermore, Accounting and Finance student pass rates for module SB102 Critical Thinking for Business are favourably higher or equivalent to students who entered DCU outside of the QQI-FET route for three of the four available academic year outcomes.

5.2 Research Limitations

The following section presents the research limitations the research team encountered during this study. Limitations include challenges with the potential student recruitment sample, student knowledge of entry routes and availability of quantitative data on QQI-FET entrants previous educational attainment. At present, data specific to QQI-FET entrants on previous FET College attended and major award used to gain entry to DCU is not captured within the available QIIO data.

5.2.1 Potential sample cohort reduction

Due to circumstances beyond the control of the research team, student recruitment could not take place from the Computer Science programme. Given the Computer Science cohort has had a larger intake of QQI-FET applicants in comparison to the Accounting and Finance programme, this barrier reduced the potential qualitative interview sample size from 25 to ten QQI-FET undergraduate entrants studying on DC115 and DC121.

5.2.2 Knowledge of previous educational attainment and entry routes

To make signing up for the study as confidential as possible students had the option to complete a register of interest form. As part of this process, it became evident students may not be aware of their previous educational attainment achievements, due to the gaps in educational engagement over time. From further correspondence with a respondent, it was acknowledged that they were not sure about which award they had received prior to entering DCU. Another respondent also indicated an uncertainty about previous educational attainment. This finding flags the complexity of routes into DCU, for example students may use their QQI credentials on one route, their mature student status on another. Students are informed on which basis they have been offered a place, but some do not focus on what route qualifies as the successful route for them. This is supported by the literature which suggests students may not always be aware how they gained entry

to university (Rami et al., 2016). This in turn may negatively have impacted student engagement in the research as they no longer defined or categorised themselves as QQI-FET students, but simply as DCU successful applicants.

5.2.3 Limitations in current quantitative data collection

Through consultation with the QIIO it has been made clear the current available data collected in relation to QQI-FET entrants is limited and does not include significant information such as previous educational institutions attended or which QQI major award was used to gain entry to DCU. This gap in current data collection makes tracking access, transfer and progression between FET and higher education challenging. Furthermore, if student progression patterns could be identified, this information may provide opportunities for DCU to work alongside FET Colleges to ensure QQI-FET applicants are prepared for the academic standards required at third level.

5.2.4 Challenges obtaining quantitative data

The research team experienced challenges in obtaining access to required quantitative data. Initial quantitative data obtained in October 2023 provided minimal information on the number of QQI-FET entrants and an overview of student's overall average precision marks. Given the small sample cohort size and the findings in the literature which suggests certain components of higher education are more challenging for QQI-FET learners such as mathematics module standards, further quantitative information was required to understand student academic outcomes. There were significant time delays and challenges in relation to accessing, viewing and interpreting the quantitative data from this period. Despite these challenges the research team engaged with the Quality and Institutional Insights Office (QIIO) from December 2023 until July 2024. A final follow up data clarification meeting took place with the QIIO in late July 2024.

5.3 Summary and Conclusion

The key findings and research limitations of this report have been outlined in this section. Drawing findings from available quantitative and qualitative data, the research shows financial implications of higher education negatively impact QQI-FET to HE transitions. While acceptance and retention outcomes within the first year QQI-FET student cohort are strong, students entering HE with a QQI qualification experience academic

challenges in particular subject disciplines. In contrast, within this report QQI-FET entrants have been shown to surpass other entrant cohorts such as HEAR and DARE applicants in non-mathematics and laboratory-based modules. While this report presents many findings in the areas of retention and academic outcomes there are a number of limitations which restricted the availability of data such as access for recruitment purposes to the intended sample cohort and uncertainty of access routes within the study body.

6 Discussion and Recommendations

The following section presents recommendations to support the improvement of QQI-FET entrant outcomes for first year undergraduate DCU students studying Accounting and Finance and Computer Science. Recommendations have been drawn from analysis of available quantitative and qualitative data specific to QQI-FET students' academic outcomes and transition experiences of FET to HE. The chapter concludes with an overall discussion of the main points highlighted in this report.

6.1 Discussion

This report captures the QQI-FET entrant student experience of entering DCU as a first year undergraduate student on two specific programmes, DC115 Accounting and Finance and DC121 Computer Science. To gain insights into the QQI-FET entrant transitions and HE engagement experience this study captured the students' journey focusing on the challenges and the potential available supports in place during the progression and settling-in period as a first year undergraduate DCU student. Through a combination of qualitative and quantitative analysis, the research identified areas where QQI-FET entrants face difficulties, such as in specific academic modules disciplines of mathematics and practical-based modules. While there are apparent academic challenges for QQI-FET entrants, other elements of academic outcomes show this student cohort is stronger in particular academic subjects in comparison to other student cohorts such as HEAR, DARE and Sports Scholarship applicants. Exploring the wider FET to HE transition process the report identified gaps in the potential availability of guidance at pre-entry level which may impact knowledge of progression routes and available financial third level supports. Furthermore, student engagement during the data collection recruitment phase suggests undergraduate students may not always be aware of the variety of access routes available for entry to higher education. The lack of clarity about access routes and poor societal perceptions of FET may have negatively impacted the student recruitment process. While this report does capture the QQI-FET student experience as intended it is important to note the findings and recommendations are primarily based upon available quantitative and secondary qualitative data. Although numerous student recruitment approaches were adopted, only one QQI-FET undergraduate student opted to take part in this study. While this outcome has implications for the findings and recommendations, the student recruitment process highlighted potential gaps in information and guidance therefore resulting in findings specific to the QQI-FET to HE experience.

The findings show FET to HE acceptance rates are high within the FET to DCU CAO offer process. This may suggest DCU is seen as a popular choice for QQI-FET entrants. Furthermore, this finding may be a consequence of DCU's commitment to QQI-FET student recruitment approaches which include DCU staff visits to PLC Colleges and a dedicated DCU QQI-FET Annual Open day. Although QQI-FET to DCU acceptance rates are high the available data shows students who progress to DC115 and DC121 using a QQI-FET route are less likely to have attended a DEIS post-primary school. This finding is in line with previous studies which show students who experience socio-economic disadvantage are less likely to progress from FET to higher education.

6.2 Recommendations

The following recommendations aim to improve the QQI-FET to DCU student experience with a particular focus on increasing academic outcomes for the first year undergraduate students studying DC115 and DC121. The following suggested developments may also be of relevance to the wider QQI-FET to DCU student cohort.

- **Enhance support for students with DEIS school experience to increase progression from FET to HE**

Recommendation: Consider implementing targeted support programmes for students who previously attended DEIS schools who are applying through the QQI-FET entry route. This could involve providing additional guidance and resources to help overcome the socio-economic disadvantages that may impact their progression to higher education. Additional resources could take the form of pre-entry writing or mathematics week workshops to improve academic outcomes and social integration.

Rationale: The findings tentatively suggest that students progressing onto DC115 and DC121 through the QQI-FET route are less likely to have attended DEIS schools. Adding enhanced information and resources for DEIS school students could enhance diversity and accessibility in higher education and increase HE participation from target cohort groups identified in the current National Access Plan 2022-2028 (HEA, 2022).

- **Increase qualitative data collection from the QQI-FET entrant cohort within DCU**

Recommendation: Conduct additional qualitative research to explore the trends observed in the quantitative data. Specifically, investigate the experiences of QQI-FET entrants, particularly in terms of their academic challenges and the support they receive. Widen the potential qualitative cohort to include QQI-FET entrants on all years of the selected programmes to develop a longitudinal overview of the FET to HE experience.

Rationale: The current study's reliance on quantitative data limits the depth of understanding regarding QQI-FET students' experiences. More qualitative data could provide richer insights and help develop more effective interventions.

- **Ensure that transparent information specific to which entry route was the basis for a DCU offer is provided to each student during the registration process**

Recommendation: Students should be provided with clear information on entry route basis during the registration process phase. This could be implemented during the online registration process and reinforced at the point of obtaining a student ID card.

Rationale: The current study indicates students who apply to University on the basis of multiple entry routes on the CAO may not be fully aware of which grounds they have been granted access from. A lack of access route knowledge may have impacted student recruitment within this study and may continue to impact student recruitment in the future. Knowledge of entry route requirement is also important to ensure students are fully aware of potential targeted available supports for widening participation cohorts.

- **Strengthen academic support for QQI-FET entrants in the areas of mathematics and laboratory-based modules**

Recommendation: Develop targeted academic support programmes, especially in mathematics and practical-based modules, for first year QQI-FET entrants. This could include tutoring, workshops, and increased access to laboratory facilities. To ensure effectiveness and impact the suggested programmes should be provided throughout year one of entry.

Rationale: The lower pass rates of QQI-FET entrants in these areas highlight a need for additional academic support to ensure these students can succeed in higher education.

- **Explore the provision of access to professional guidance in FET and Post-Primary settings**

Recommendation: Explore the availability and consistency of professional guidance counselling in Further Education and Training (FET) and post-primary settings, with a particular focus on progression pathways to higher education.

Rationale: The literature suggests that access to guidance counselling may hinder FET students' ability to navigate their progression to higher education. While at FET level there is an increased focus on enhancing post-primary guidance knowledge of FET options for school leavers, specific information on navigating routes from FET to HE needs to be addressed at post-primary guidance level (SOLAS, 2020). Investigating this gap could improve student outcomes and satisfaction.

- **Enhance data collection to improve clarity on the transition from FET to HE for students and institutions.**

Recommendation: Collaborate with FET institutions and relevant offices to improve data collection on QQI-FET entrants. This could include tracking students' educational backgrounds, major awards used for entry, and their progression through higher education.

Rationale: Better data would allow for more accurate tracking of QQI-FET entrants and their academic progress, enabling institutions to tailor support services more effectively.

- **Promote the availability financial and academic supports for DCU students through a range of communication channels**

Recommendation: Create networks between various DCU stakeholders such as DCU student union, student support and development, and academic staff to develop best practice in the dissemination of information on available academic and financial supports for QQI-FET undergraduate students.

Rationale: Considering the volume of emails students receive and drawing on the zero response the research team experienced through student email contact it may be impactful to explore other information dissemination approaches when communicating with DCU students.

- **Review and address potential barriers to study participation within the DCU undergraduate landscape**

Recommendation: Consider reviewing the processes for recruiting students to participate in studies like this one, ensuring that students are fully aware of their educational achievements and entry routes.

Rationale: The confusion among students regarding their educational backgrounds may have affected their participation in the study, which suggests a need for clearer communication and support in this area.

- **Explore partnerships with FET Colleges to increase academic outcomes for QQI-FET entrant cohort**

Recommendation: Foster stronger partnerships with FET colleges to prepare QQI-FET applicants for the academic standards required at third level. This could involve joint initiatives, bridging courses, or preparatory workshops. Drawing insights from collaborative transition programmes currently within the FET to HE sector could support the development of potential partnership initiatives.

Rationale: By continuing to develop relations with FET colleges, higher education institutions can help ensure that QQI-FET entrants are better prepared for the challenges of higher education, leading to improved academic outcomes.

The recommendations presented in this report provide suggestions which aim to support a smoother transition and improved academic and non-academic experience for QQI-FET entrants to DCU and other higher education institutions. Recommendations include the development of enhanced academic supports for widening participation cohorts who enter DCU via a QQI-FET entrant route. Furthermore, in the wider context of QQI-FET to DCU transitions developing strong connections with FET providers could potentially improve the student transition experience and potentially increasing QQI-FET to DCU student transitions.

6.3 Summary

This report aimed to capture the student experience of transitioning from FET to DCU through a QQI-FET entrant route onto two specific DCU first year undergraduate programmes, DC115 Accounting and Finance and DC121 Computer science. While the report somewhat captures the QQI-FET entrants' academic outcomes through the presentation of quantitative data, unfortunately due to limited qualitative data collection other aims which included understanding the registration and CAO process from the QQI-FET student perspective could not be achieved. Challenges accessing the selected student cohorts and potential gaps in student awareness of university entry route achievements negatively impacted student participation in this study. Unfortunately, these challenges resulted in only one student taking part in a qualitative interview. While the report acknowledges the student's contribution to the research, there is insignificant qualitative data to draw inference from. As a consequence, the findings in this report draw heavily upon available literature and quantitative data received from the QIIO office in DCU. Findings drawn from quantitative data show DCU has a high acceptance rate of places offered to potential QQI-FET entrant students. This finding contrasts with previous studies in the FET to HE context. Furthermore, acceptance offer outcomes indicates DCU's commitment to widening participation for QQI-FET entrants. Information on QQI-FET entrants previous educational attainment indicates students using this route for entry into university are less likely to have attended a DEIS school setting. While the data shows QQI-FET entrants have lower academic outcomes in mathematics and laboratory-based modules, QQI-FET entrants are on a par with, and are sometimes more successful in certain modules than, students entering DCU via standard CAO and other entry routes.

While this research has contributed towards understanding the QQI-FET to DCU student experience in the context of two specific programmes DC115 Accounting and Finance and DC121 Computer Science this study highlights the need for further research in the areas of QQI-FET entrant experience of information and guidance specific to FET to HE transitions and additional qualitative data collection within the wider QQI-FET entrant DCU undergraduate student cohort.

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Appendix A Interview Schedule

Pre entry

1. Which PLC college and course did you attend?
2. Why did you choose to apply to university? Did you have any concerns or worries about attending college?
3. At what point in your journey did you decide to apply to university?

Information and Guidance

4. Where did you get information about applying to DCU/other university courses?
5. Did you find the information/guidance you received got useful?
6. Do you have any suggestions on how information and guidance on pathways from FET to university could be improved?

Application System

7. How did you find the CAO application process? Did you find it easy to understand?
8. How did you find the DCU registration process? Was it easy to navigate?
9. Did you ever have any contact with registry staff? Did you find the staff supportive?

DCU student experience

Looking back at your university experience to date

10. How have you found the academic side of college?
Have there been any elements of academic student life which you find easier than expected or any elements more challenging?
11. In relation to your overall DCU student life experience, how has it been?
Have you enjoyed being a DCU student? Have you encountered any challenges?
12. Have you used any of the available DCU student support services?
If so, did you find the services useful?

13. Are there any additional supports you think DCU should provide for students?

14. Looking back to your FET experience do you feel taking a QQI course helped your transition to DCU in any way?

Appendix B Interview schedule reflection prompt

Student Life

Social interactions with peers/staff/lecturers/tutors

Clubs and Societies

Students Union

Orientation week

Accommodation

Navigating campus/timetables

Work/life balance

Financial

Commuting

Volunteering

Academic student experience

Academic writing

Referencing

Maths

Research skills

Range of assessments- exams, group work

Teaching and Learning

Loop

Course content

Study skills-time management

Student support services

Academic supports- writing centre, maths learning centre, library workshops

Wellbeing workshops

Pastoral supports- DCU Chaplaincy

Counselling and Personal development services

Student health services- GP/Nurse

Career service

Appendix C Student recruitment presentation

FET to DCU Research Project

DCU and Further Education and Training

61 undergraduate DCU programmes with FET/PLC entry routes

DCU FET open day- tailored specifically to students studying in FET/PLC courses

FETRC Centre- Further Education and Training Research Centre

Capture the student experience of DCU students who have previously studied at a Further Education and Training College/taken a PLC course

QQI Qualification FET/PLC Route

Students who have completed a QQI level 5 or 6 major award

Qualifications & Assessment Summary :

Please tick the qualification/assessment categories that are relevant to you.
You may tick more than one box, if necessary.

1. Irish Leaving Certificate Exams (1985-2024) [Help?](#)
2. QQI FET/FETAC Level 5/6 Exams (2002-2024) [Help?](#)
(Including Post-Leaving Certificate Courses leading to QQI FET/FETAC level 5 or 6 awards)
3. GCE A/AS Levels/GCSE (2006-2024) [Help?](#)
(England, Wales, Northern Ireland Exams, and International GCE/GCSE Exams under CAIE, PEARSON, AQA, OCR Boards)
4. Other School Leaving Exams [Help?](#)
(e.g. School Leaving Exams outside of UK & Ireland, Baccalaureate, Scottish Exams, pre-1985 Irish & UK exams, Leaving Cert Applied, Level 3 BTEC, GNVQs, VCEs, Irish Matric Exams, GCE/GCSE pre-2006, etc. - see "Help?" link for further information)
5. Other Further Education [Help?](#)
(Any other Further Education courses that you have undertaken that do not fall into one of the other categories on this application form. See "Help?" link for further information.)
6. Third-Level Higher Education [Help?](#)
(required regardless of whether you passed, failed, or did not take examinations)
7. Mature Applicants [Help?](#)
(those 23 years of age on or before the 1st of January 2024)

Logistics- How, Where, When, Who

One to one interviews with Sarah- Confidential and anonymized

Online via DCU zoom or in person on DCU campus

40 minutes to 1 hour- time that works for you- Late January/early February 2024

Compensation for loss of earnings- €30.00 for taking part

Discussion topics

FET/PLC experience-
University prep

Applying to University - CAO
application to DCU
registration

DCU Student experience-
academic; student life;
student supports

Why take part?

- Contribute to improving student experience in DCU
- Reflect on your success to date

What will happen after the interview?

- Findings will be presented in a report

How did I sign up?

SCAN QR code on flyer or email or call/text/whatsapp Sarah for more information

Email

sarah.mcmanus@dcu.ie

Phone/text/whatsapp

0851726261

Thanks for your time

Questions?

Appendix D Recruitment Flyer

**ARE YOU A DCU STUDENT WHO HAS
PREVIOUSLY STUDIED AT A FURTHER
EDUCATION COLLEGE OR COMPLETED A PLC
COURSE?**

**Would you like to take part in a one to one
interview about your college experience?**

**TAKING PLACE FEBRUARY & MARCH
2024**

**SCAN HERE TO REGISTER
YOUR INTEREST IN TAKING
PART**

**€30 VOUCHER TO THANK YOU
FOR YOUR TIME**

For more information contact
Sarah on email/phone/text/whatsapp
sarah.mcmanus@dcu.ie
085 1726261

Appendix E Google forms Register of interest application

FET/PLC to DCU Student Experience Research Study

Please complete the following form if you are interested in taking part in this research study.

1. Full Name
2. Active Email Address
3. Current DCU course of study
4. Did you complete a PLC course at a FET College prior to entering DCU on your current course of study? Please select one answer
 - Yes
 - No
 - Not sure
5. Did you achieve a QQI level 5 or level 6 major award qualification prior to becoming a DCU student? Please select one answer
 - Yes I completed a QQI level 5 major award
 - Yes I completed a QQI level 6 major award
 - No I didn't complete a QQI level 5 or 6 major award
 - Not sure

Appendix F DC115 & DC121 QOI-FET student programme offers and acceptances

Cohort	Cohort included	Offered place	Accepted place	Acceptance rate
2023/2024	DC115 & DC121	23	23	100%
2022/2023	DC115 & DC121	33	25	75.7%
2021/2022	DC115	12	10	83.3%
2020/2021	DC115	10	10	100%
2019/2020	DC115	6	6	100%
Totals		84	74	88%

Appendix G DC115 FET entrant retention rates comparing September to March enrolment 2019/20 to 2023/24

Appendix H DC121 FET entrant retention rates comparing September to March enrolment 2022/23 & 2023/24

Appendix I County breakdown of schools attended by FET entrants on DC115 and DC121

County	No. of Post primary schools in recorded	No. of students who attended	County	No. of Post primary schools recorded	No. of students who attended
Dublin	18	24	Monaghan	2	2
Meath	9	12	Kildare	1	1
Louth	7	12	Offaly	1	1
Cavan	2	4	Wicklow	1	1
Westmeath	2	2	Unknown	1	1

**Appendix J DC121 Acceptance of places by gender-
September data for each academic entrant year**

Academic year	Offered places Female cohort	Accepted places Female cohort	Offered places Male cohort	Accepted places Male cohort
2022/2023	2	2	18	13
2023/2024	5	5	10	10
Totals	7	7	28	23

Appendix K APM outcomes for year one DC121 students in the academic year 2022/2023

Appendix L APM outcomes for year one DC115 students in the academic years 2019/2020 to 2022/2023

